

ARTICLE

A CUSUM Control Chart for Gamma Distribution with cautious parameter learning

Harold Manuel Madrid-Alvarez¹^c

^a School of Engineering, Universidad Simón Bolívar, Barranquilla, Colombia; ^b Department of Applied Statistics and Operational Research and Quality, Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, España; ^c School of Engineering and Sciences, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Monterrey, Nuevo León, Mexico

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ABSTRACT

The study and monitoring of production processes have traditionally focused on normal distributions, often overlooking non-normal or skewed ones. This tendency is particularly pronounced in scenarios like cycle times and processes subject to single specification limits. In these instances, gamma distributions more accurately encapsulate the data's behavior. It is here that CUSUM control charts can achieve optimal performance in detecting shifts in known in-control parameters. However, in practice, gamma parameters need to be estimated, and limited samples during Phase I can lead to undesirable Phase II performance, measured as the *average run length* (ARL). Guaranteed performance approaches solve this issue at the expense of power. To address this undesirable situation, our study introduces the implementation of a CUSUM control chart for the Gamma distribution with cautious parameter learning. Using Montecarlo simulations, we assess the ARL of a CUSUM scheme designed to monitor scale changes with estimated parameters. This paper highlights the efficacy of ARL performance in the presence of a cautious learning approach to improve parameters estimation. We compare performance under in-control and out-of-control conditions, emphasizing the guaranteed conditional in-control performance of our cautious learning proposal. Finally, we demonstrate the practical applicability of this methodology in a packaging process using multi-head weighing machines. This research offers professionals interested in reliable monitoring schemes a set of guidelines for implementation, including algorithms and reference tables

KEYWORDS

Control Chart, Estimated Parameters, Cautious Parameter Learning, Gamma Distribution

1. Introduction

Quality control theory has been a significant area of study in statistics for decades. Control charts are an essential tool in this field, providing an effective way to monitor production processes and detect any significant changes in product quality. In particular, the *cumulative sum* CUSUM control chart has proven to be a powerful tool for detecting small shifts in a process mean. Its optimality property to detect specific changes in a process makes it an attractive choice for researchers and practitioners.

CONTACT Víctor G. Tercero-Gómez. Email: victor.tercero@tec.mx

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The CUSUM chart, undoubtedly one of the most widely used control charts for the detection of minimal and moderate changes, was initially proposed by Page in 1954. The analysis of these charts has been carried out over the years by various authors, highlighting the contributions of Woodall and Adams (1993), among others, who have conducted exhaustive studies on this tool.

For this study we use a CUSUM control chart tailored for the gamma distribution (Alamer 2017). The Gamma distribution is a continuous probability distribution commonly used to model waiting times and product lifetimes. In this context, the CUSUM control chart for the Gamma distribution can be a valuable tool for monitoring product quality and reliability over time. However, implementing a CUSUM control chart for the Gamma distribution can be challenging due to the need to estimate the parameters of the Gamma distribution. This is a common problem in statistical quality control, as accurate parameter estimation is essential for the performance of the control chart. According to Huberts, Goedhart, and Does (2022), this situation creates uncertainty in the performance of the charts. The repercussions of this uncertainty have been the subject of substantial research in recent years, leading to proposed solutions to mitigate this issue. Jensen et al. (2006) and Psarakis, Vyniou, and Castagliola (2014) conducted bibliographic reviews on parameter estimation in control charts, thus identifying areas for future research. In recent years, various researchers have suggested adjusted control chart designs that are based on guaranteed performance during the control phase (see, for example, Zago and Capizzi (2023); Capizzi and Masarotto (2020); Gandy and Kvaløy (2013); Saleh et al. (2015); Saleh and Mahmoud (2017); Goedhart, Schoonhoven, and Does (2017); Goedhart et al. (2017); Chakraborti (2006); Zwetsloot and Ajadi (2019); Diko, Chakraborti, and Does (2019)). Extending on the concept of guaranteed performance, Capizzi and Masarotto (2020) proposed a “cautious learning” approach to improve parameter estimation. This approach involves updating parameter estimates as more data is collected, but in a way that minimizes the risk of data contamination by out-of-control observations.

Cautious learning can be particularly useful in the context of CUSUM control charts for the Gamma distribution, as these charts are sensitive to changes in the distribution parameters. By updating parameter estimates cautiously, the sensitivity of the CUSUM control chart to detect shifts in the process mean can be maintained, while minimizing the risk of false alarms due to random fluctuations in the data.

In this work, we aim to expand the methodology proposed by Capizzi and Masarotto (2020), which has been studied by Li (2022), Huberts, Goedhart, and Does (2022) and Zago and Capizzi (2023), by examining the impacts of delays that arise when updating parameter estimates while monitoring problems following a gamma distribution, such as time between events and other asymmetric processes. Our strategy involves the use of an optimized CUSUM control chart design. The inspiration for our research comes from the studies of García-Díaz and Pulido-Rojano (2017), where measurements of multiple weighings in a packaging process fit a gamma model and require monitoring.

In recent times, when parameters are estimated, the emphasis has shifted towards selecting a value for the control limit that ensures a certain likelihood that the *in-control* (IC) *average run length* (ARL) will be at least as a desired target ARL value. (Gandy and Kvaløy 2013; Jones and Steiner 2012; Saleh et al. 2015; Goedhart, Schoonhoven, and Does 2017). In this context, control limits are determined such that

$$P\{ARL_s > (1 - a)ARL_0\} = 1 - b, \quad (1)$$

where the ARL_s is the ARL given the sample used to calibrate the chart, ARL_0 is the

expected/target IC ARL, and $0 \leq \alpha, \beta \leq 1$. Since the ARL_s is a value calculated from a given Phase I sample, and might change from sample to sample, ARL_s is a random variable, prone to sample variation.

Traditional control chart approaches consider a static Phase I sample, where IC observations are used to estimate parameters and set up for a Phase II scheme – actual process monitoring. However, it’s a fact that Phase II data, when in control, can be used to improve estimation and adjust control limits accordingly. The process of updating the estimates for the process parameters could take place after each new observation, this is the case of self-starting approaches (Hawkins 1987; Quesenberry 1991; Keefe, Woodall, and Jones-Farmer 2015). Following this idea, research by Huberts, Schoonhoven, and Does (2019, 2020) and Huberts, Goedhart, and Does (2022) reported that updating is frequently a beneficial strategy. However, the results are contingent on the practitioners’ ability to retrospectively identify out-of-control samples to avoid contamination when re-estimating the parameters. One potential risk of an updating scheme is that minor shifts may not be immediately detected, resulting in out-of-control observations being used in the updated in-control parameter estimates. This contamination might create biases that can hinder a desired monitoring performance. As a solution, we can introduce a delay in the estimation update process, as proposed by Capizzi and Masarotto (2020). The impact of updating the control limits on the performance of the control chart is heavily dependent on Phase I sample size m , shift size δ , target IC performance ARL_0 , the type of chart, and the decisions made by practitioners regarding the data and the timing of updates.

Capizzi and Masarotto (2020) proposed a method of updating the estimated parameters of the mean and standard deviation with a delay and a preliminary IC assessment. Let the monitoring start at time $i = 1$, at some time $i \geq 1$, if it is reasonable to assume the process is in control, newly collected observations could be used to update estimates of the mean and standard deviation parameters. This reduces the uncertainty associated with estimation. The timing of an update could be predetermined, or determined using the collected new samples. For the latter, Capizzi and Masarotto (2020) proposed the cumulative sum and inequality

$$\sum_{j=i+d_i+1}^i \left(\frac{x_j - \bar{x}_{i-d_i}}{S_{i-d_i}} \right)^2 < Ad_i - B \quad (2)$$

as a condition for updating estimates, A.K.A. learning, where d_i counts the number of samples from the last update, and A and B are suitable positive constants. Left-side of this inequality corresponds to the kernel of a loglikelihood of a normal sequence of i.i.d.r.v., where values smaller than $Ad_i - B$ provide evidence for an in-control state assuming the true mean and variance are \bar{x}_{i-d_i} and variance $S_{i-d_i}^2$, correspondingly.

Alternatively, Li (2022) introduced a novel cautious learning scheme based on a CUSUM approach, which, in turn, is based on the evaluation of the likelihood function. As the CUSUM is based on the sequential probability ratio test by Wald (1945). A CUSUM hitting zero provides evidence that favors the in-control hypothesis, while the control limits remains to conclude in favor of the out-of-control alternative. The CUSUM structure facilitates the evaluation of the likelihood function, and provides a framework to address parameter learning over time. Li (2022) implemented this learning approach for the monitoring of normal series using an adaptive version of a CUSUM to keep the approach sensitive over varying shift sizes when the process is out of control.

Let X_{-m+1}, \dots, X_0 be a Phase I IC sample, which follows a Gamma distribution with shape parameters α_0 and scale β_0 . This behavior continues over a Phase II until a change occurs. We'll assume a sustained change that initiates at time $\tau \geq 1$, and call it change point. Starting on τ , it is assumed that the observations follow a Gamma distribution with shape parameters α_1 and scale β_1 . All observations are assumed to be independent.

To design an optimal CUSUM scheme, the values of α_0 , α_1 , β_0 , and β_1 need to be known. However, in practice, α_0 and β_0 are not available and must be estimated from an IC sample of the process – phase I sample. α_1 and β_1 are also frequently unknown, and practitioners set these values to coincide with the smallest change in the process that is practical to address. Phase II observations are considered in an unknown state. Before τ , they are IC, after τ , they are OC, but τ is unknown. If τ is known, the problem of learning is reduced to update parameters using observations $i < \tau$ to maximize the probability to detect a change during the analysis of $i \geq \tau$ observations.

As seen in the following section, to allow learning when IC state is uncertain, a parallel CUSUM scheme, where L^+ and L^- are the names given to these plotting CUSUM statistics, can be added to assess the IC likelihood. While a CUSUM with plotting statistics C^+ and C^- is used to provide a signal for an OC state, L^+ and L^- can be used to provide a signal for an IC state. L^+ and L^- are used for cautious learning. Of course, C^+ and C^- can be used as L^+ and L^- to achieve a learning and OC monitoring with a reduced scheme, only one CUSUM, however, we keep OC monitoring and learning decoupled during the manuscript to reduce confusion and allow more flexibility, as both CUSUMs can be calibrated independently. These statistics are updated as new observations are collected. Page's 1954 CUSUM can be interpreted as a series of *sequential probability ratio tests* (SPRTs) (Lorden 1971; Moustakides 1986; Hawkins and Olwell 1998). This can be seen as these plotting statistics are based on a loglikelihood $Z_i = \log[f_1(X_i)/f_0(X_i)]$.

For an in-depth exploration of the SPRT, one might consult Price (1948) or Siegmund (1985). In the traditional SPRT structure, a straightforward null hypothesis H_0 is evaluated against a simple alternative hypothesis, H_1 . However, with a SPRT approach each new observation is evaluated, yielding three potential outcomes:

- Stop sampling and accept H_0 .
- Stop sampling and accept H_1 .
- Continue sampling if there is not enough evidence to conclude.

Conditions to accept H_0 or H_1 are defined with type I and type II error rates in mind.

CUSUM charts do not explicitly confirm the null hypothesis, H_0 , when the evidence is in its favor, i.e., when the cumulative sum, $C_j \leq 0$. Rather, in such instances, the sum is reset to 0 and the test restarts. The sampling process persists until there is sufficient evidence to dismiss H_0 , i.e., when $C_j > h$, where h is a decision limit.

This paper is divided as follows. In Section 2, we discuss the design of the CUSUM control chart designs, description of the methodology to update the control limits and control chart performance, Section 3 set out the applied case, and some final considerations and ideas for future research, respectively.

2. Proposed Monitoring Scheme

2.1. Preliminaries

In this section, we detail the application of a CUSUM scheme for the Gamma distribution. Let's denote x_i as the data point at time i . We assume that in phase I, we have an in-control set of m observations independently and identically distributed as $\Gamma(\alpha, \beta_0)$. Here α is shape parameter and β_j is a scale parameter. Also, measurements in phase II follow the same behavior when the process is in-control and a shift to an out-of-control state might happen at change-point τ where observations start to follow a $\Gamma(\alpha, \beta_1)$.

Typically in practice, α and β_j are unknown quantities. While a broad array of estimators may be applied, for the purpose of this study, we utilize the maximum likelihood estimator. When α is known

$$\hat{\beta}_0 = \frac{\bar{X}}{\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

where \bar{X} is the average of a phase I sample. In order to approximate α , a numerical method is employed, specifically the Newton technique, by approximating the root of the likelihood equation. (Shenton and Bowman 1982)

$$g(\alpha) = -n\psi(\alpha) - n\log\bar{x} + n\log\alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i, \quad (4)$$

through the succession of

$$\alpha_m = \alpha_{m-1} \left(1 + \frac{\psi(\alpha_{m-1}) + \log\bar{x} - \log(\alpha_{m-1}) - \overline{\log x}}{1 - \alpha_{m-1}\psi'(\alpha_{m-1})} \right), \quad (5)$$

where the function ψ and ψ' are a digamma and trigamma function respectively, and $\overline{\log x} = \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i / n$. Moment estimator $\alpha_o = \bar{x}^2 / s^2$ is used to initialize the search. Here, s^2 is the sample variance.

2.2. CUSUM-Gamma control chart with known parameters

The CUSUM control chart for the Gamma distribution is a statistical quality control tool used to detect changes in a process that follows a Gamma distribution. The Gamma distribution plays a pivotal role in statistical process control, encompassing the chi-square and exponential distributions as specific instances (Qiu 2013). It provides a model for numerous compelling applications in service and manufacturing processes. The probability density function of the Gamma distribution (PDF) is defined as follows:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\beta^\alpha} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta}} \quad \alpha, \beta > 0, \quad (6)$$

where α is a shape parameter and β a scale parameter. The mean and variance of this function are $\alpha\beta$ and $\alpha\beta^2$, respectively. This distribution is extensively used for data with asymmetric behavior in particular when it is skewed toward the right

side.(Woodall 1984; Huang et al. 2016; Kazemi et al. 2021; Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz, and Tercero-Gómez 2023).

In the context of the CUSUM control chart, we assume that the in-control (IC) distribution of the process is the Gamma distribution with parameters α_0 and β_0 . When the process experiences abnormal variations at the change point τ , the out-of-control (OC) distribution is assumed to be Gamma with parameters α_1 and β_1 , where $\alpha_1 \neq \alpha_0$ or $\beta_1 \neq \beta_0$.

When our focus is on identifying an upward shift in β from β_0 to β_1 , where $\beta_0 < \beta_1$, then the charting statistic for an optimal CUSUM chart is determined by

$$C_i^+ = \max(0, C_{i-1}^+ + X_i - k^+). \quad (7)$$

While for a downward shift, $\beta_0 > \beta_1$, then,

$$C_i^- = \min(0, C_{i-1}^- + X_i - k^-), \quad (8)$$

where $C_0^+ = C_0^- = 0$. For optimal performance k^+ follows

$$k^+ = -\frac{\alpha\beta_0\beta_1 \log\left(\frac{\beta_0}{\beta_1}\right)}{\beta_1 - \beta_0}. \quad (9)$$

k^- has the same expression as k^+ , but we use $\beta_1 < \beta_0$ instead of $\beta_1 > \beta_0$.

A signal is triggered if either $C_i^- \leq -h^-$ or $C_i^+ \geq h^+$, where the critical values h^- and h^+ are positive constants defined to obtain a desired in-control behavior. Practitioners can choose to monitor both C_i^+ and C_i^- statistics for a two side monitoring or decide for a single side if required.

Considering that $Z = X/\beta_0$ follows a gamma distribution with a unit scale $\beta_0 = 1$, critical values for Z reduce the need for, otherwise, redundant tables. Traditional control chart design would recommend choosing value of h^- and h^+ that yield a desired in-control ARL.

2.3. Proposed CUSUM-Gamma monitoring with cautious parameter learning and guaranteed in-control performance with unknown parameters

This subsection presents a detailed analysis of the proposed algorithm for Gamma-CUSUM monitoring incorporating cautious learning and guaranteed control limits, particularly in scenarios with unknown parameters α and β . The procedure, summarized at the end in algorithm 1, is structured into several key stages, each meticulously designed to ensure effective monitoring and cautious updates of the gamma distribution parameters. Procedure is focused on the monitoring of upward changes to reduce complexity describing the method. Nevertheless, adjustments for a downward CUSUM are indicated thru the text.

2.3.1. Stage 1: Preamble

In this initial stage, the CUSUM monitoring statistic, C_0^+ , and the learning statistic L_0^+ are initialized at 0. Phase I sample size is defined as m . Indices l , q , and i are also initialized at 0. $l \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ defines the last moment in which learning occurred for

the upward CUSUM. $i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ is an index of the time of phase II observations. $q \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ count how many observations since the last learning occurred, hence $i = l + q$. Guaranteed performance parameters $0 \leq a, b \leq 1$ are set ensure an exceedance probability (1). Learning parameters, k_L^+ and d^+ , are also determined in this phase. Recommended values $k_L^+ = 2$ and $d^+ = 25$ are suggested as they offer protection and high power to detect a change. A sensitivity analysis of these values is addressed subsections below. d^+ controls the minimum delay before any learning can happen, and k_L^+ establish how much variability is allowed to consider a process in-control.

2.3.2. Stage 2: Phase I - Setup

A sample of m in-control (IC) observations is collected to establish a baseline for parameter estimations. Parameters are estimated using $\hat{\alpha}_l^+$ and $\hat{\beta}_l^+$ by following techniques described in equations (3) and (5).

For a downward CUSUM the same is done for $\hat{\alpha}_l^-$ and $\hat{\beta}_l^-$. Before monitoring starts $\hat{\alpha}_l^+ = \hat{\alpha}_l^-$ and $\hat{\beta}_l^+ = \hat{\beta}_l^-$, however, estimations might differ once learning at different times happens for each chart, upward and downward CUSUM.

Depending on the phase I sample size and the value of α_0 , we define a value for Δ_h^+ . This is a correction made to control limits used to ensure a minimum IC performance. Derivation of Δ_h^+ is done using Algorithm 2, however, tables are available in Appendix A). Practitioners can use interpolation if necessary. If α_0 is unknown, use $\hat{\alpha}_0^+$, the value estimated from phase I. This is analogous to a bootstrap estimation, where initial estimate is used as baseline for the simulation, and table values were considered using the added uncertainty. Finally, the control limit for the upward CUSUM is calculated using

$$H_l^+ = h^+ + \Delta_h^+ \left(\sqrt{\frac{m}{m+l}} \right)^{1.7}, \quad (10)$$

This limit is adjusted over time, decreasing as the number of observations used for parameter estimation increases. l corresponds to the number of observations from Phase II monitoring used for learning. Before monitoring starts $l = 0$, but it changes as described in following sub-subsection, when learning occurs. This gradual reduction is a critical feature of the algorithm, allowing for more precise monitoring and reducing the likelihood of false alarms as more information is gathered. The rate of decrease of these limits follows the rate of correction decline to ensure minimum in-control performance as proposed by Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz, and Tercero-Gómez (2023). Similar instructions follow a downward CUSUM to monitor plotting statistic (8). In this case, control limit used corresponds to

$$H_l^- = h^- - \Delta_h^- \left(\sqrt{\frac{m}{m+l}} \right)^{1.7}. \quad (11)$$

2.3.3. Stage 3: Phase II - Ongoing Monitoring and Learning

Each new observation is monitored in Phase II. Here, the CUSUM plotting statistics C_i^+ are calculated, and if $C_i^+ > H_l^+$, an out-of-control (OC) alarm is triggered. Concurrently, a learning process occurs where the learning statistic L_i^+ is calculated

as

$$L_i^+ = \max(0, L_{i-1}^+ + X_i - k_L^+). \quad (12)$$

If $q > d^+$ and $L_i^+ = 0$, the learning counters are updated ($l = i, q = 0$), allowing for the inclusion of the m Phase I observations and observed values $1, \dots, l$ from Phase II in updating the estimators $\hat{\alpha}_l^+$ and $\hat{\beta}_l^+$. Since upward and downward CUSUMs are functionally independent, learning and parameters can be done independently of each other. For the downward CUSUM, learning follows previous rules over statistic

$$L_i^- = \min(0, L_{i-1}^- + X_i - k_L^-). \quad (13)$$

Algorithm 1 Upward Gamma-CUSUM Monitoring with Cautious Learning and Guarantee In-Control Limits with unknown parameters α and β . Change $+$ to $-$ for downward CUSUM. Do $+$ and $-$ for two-sided CUSUM. Ignore α estimation if known.

- 1: Preamble.
 - Initialize: $C_0^+, L_0^+ = 0, l = 0, i = 0, q = 0$.
 - Define sample size: m .
 - Define guaranteed performance parameters: a and b .
 - Define learning parameters: k_L^+, d^+ .
 - Define monitoring parameters: h^+, k^+, Δ_h^+ .
 - 2: Phase I – Setup.
 - i. Take a sample of m IC observations.
 - ii. Estimate parameters with estimators $\hat{\alpha}_l^+$ and $\hat{\beta}_l^+$.
 - iii. Select corresponding Δ_h^+ from tables. Interpolate if necessary.
 - iv. Calculate control limit H_l^+
 - 3: Phase II – Monitoring: **WHILE** $C_i^+ \leq H_l^+$.
 - i. $i = i + 1, q = q + 1$.
 - ii. Obtain a new observation X_i .
 - iii. Monitoring:
 - a. Calculate plotting statistics C_i^+ .
 - b. If $C_i^+ > H_l^+$ then an OC alarm is triggered – exit **WHILE**.
 - iv. Learning:
 - a. Calculate learning statistic L_i^+ .
 - b. If $q > d^+$ & $L_i^+ = 0$ then $l = i, q = 0$
 - c. Update $\hat{\alpha}_l^+$ and $\hat{\beta}_l^+$ to include m observations from Phase I and $1, \dots, l$ observed values from Phase II.
-

3. Chart Design

As seen in Algorithm 1, to use our proposed approach we need to define guaranteed performance parameters a and b ; learning parameters k_L^+ and d^+ ; and monitoring parameters h^+, k^+ and Δ_h^+ .

Guaranteed performance parameters a and b , as define by equation (3) can take any values between 0 and 1 as long as they define a minimum acceptable performance. For this research we used $a = 0.1$ and $b = 0.05$ as Capizzi and Masarotto (2020); i.e.,

assuming a desired in-control target $ARL_0 = 500$, we accept ARL_0 's of 450 or more with a probability of 0.95.

The first two monitoring parameters h^+ and k^+ are defined with a limiting behavior in mind, where parameters are known. In this scenario, k^+ is defined by equation (9) where β_0 and β_1 are used as input. If we are monitoring statistic $Z = X/\beta_0$ we only need to define a value β_1 , the smallest change we want to detect, since β_0 would be 1 for a standard gamma. We chose $\beta_1 = 1.5$ and 2 for upward CUSUM and $\beta_1 = 1.5^{-1}$ and 2^{-1} for a downward CUSUM. Once k^+ is set, a value of h^+ is chosen to achieve a desired ARL_0 . Given a known value of shape parameter α , extensive Monte Carlo simulations or Markov chain models can be used to determine a h^+ . If α is unknown, practitioners can use the corresponding maximum likelihood estimator. α estimation adds uncertainty that, at some level, can be accounted for with Δ_h^+ estimation. Considering $\beta_0 = 1$, for a wide range of α values we can use equations found in Tables 1 to 4 to get accurate estimations of h^+ or h^- for different ARL_0 values of 370, 500 and 1000. These equations were calibrated for $\alpha \in (0.5, 5)$.

Table 1. Functions for h^+ with $\beta_1 = 1.5$

ARL	Function for h^+
370	$\sqrt{76.5474 + 35.6445 \cdot \ln(\alpha)}$
500	$\sqrt{91.0578 + 39.8797 \cdot \ln(\alpha)}$
1000	$\sqrt{131.375 + 49.3136 \cdot \ln(\alpha)}$

Table 2. Functions for h^+ with $\beta_1 = 2$

ARL	Function for h^+
370	$\frac{1}{0.118785 + 0.0255867/\alpha}$
500	$\frac{1}{0.111016 + 0.0222018/\alpha}$
1000	$\frac{1}{0.0963618 + 0.0166069/\alpha}$

Table 3. Function for h^- with $\beta_1 = 1.5^{-1}$

ARL	Function for h^-
370	$-6.27428 - 1.26883 \cdot \ln(\alpha)$
500	$-6.84881 - 1.27201 \cdot \ln(\alpha)$
1000	$-8.14798 - 1.31649 \cdot \ln(\alpha)$

Table 4. Function for h^- with $\beta_1 = 2^{-1}$

ARL	Function for h^-
370	$-4.59767 + 0.636209/\alpha$
500	$-4.90751 + 0.673361/\alpha$
1000	$-4.81216 - 0.482048 \cdot \ln(\alpha)$

Control limits h^+ were estimated based on the values proposed by Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz, and Tercero-Gómez (2023). If necessary, other values can be obtained following a linear interpolation. For instance, we can use

$$h^+ = h_i + \frac{h_{i+1} - h_i}{\alpha_{i+1} - \alpha_i}(\alpha - \alpha_i). \quad (14)$$

Learning parameters k_L^+ and d^+ determine how often estimators get updated. Just like a normal CUSUM k_L^+ is an allowance, when the cumulative sum is smaller or equal to this value, the CUSUM gets to zero, signalling there is scarce evidence for an OC signal, which can be interpreted as evidence in favor of the IC hypothesis, suggesting that it is safe to update parameter estimates. However, lack of evidence of a test with low power means little in favor of the null hypothesis, hence, risk of a type II error is high. To reduce this risk, $d^+ > 0$ defines a delay since the last parameter estimation. This reduces the type II error of the learning scheme as parameter estimates are updated only after the specified delay. Given any values for k_L^+ and d^+ , calibration of monitoring parameter Δ_h^+ assures a desired IC performance in terms of the ARL_0 . However, OC performance can be hindered if k_L^+ and d^+ are poorly chosen. Calculation of Δ_h^+ for any k_L^+ and d^+ followed by a sensitivity analysis of these values is required. Through experimentation, as seen later, values of $d^+ = 25$ and $k_L^+ = 2$ were identified to be appropriate for most cases.

To account for Phase I uncertainties when estimating β_0 and α , after establishing the h^+ limit, for any given values of k_L^+ and d^+ stochastic estimation in Algorithm 2 was applied to determine an appropriate correction value Δ_h^+ for the model. This value not only ensures the minimum performance of the control chart but also includes a learning component that cautiously adjusts the control limits, ensuring convergence to h^+ after n observations.

Algorithm 2 was applied with $\beta_0 = 1$ since variables were standardized with estimated β_0 . If α is known, h^+ limit is a fixed value, however, if α is estimated h^+ limit needs to be updated to obtain the *ARL* in step 4. Practitioners need to consider that this algorithm works similar to a bootstrap. This is, α and β_0 values used for the simulation are fixed, defined in step 1. However, in step 3, estimates $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}_0$ are estimated from

Algorithm 2 Algorithm for determining Δ_h^+ with learning based on stochastic approximation.

- 1: Define n , α , β_0 , β_1 , h^+ , a , b , *ARLo*, D_0 , *gam*, and the number of initial and final interactions. For this particular case, a value of $a = 0.1$, $b = 0.05$, $D_0 = \frac{h}{10}$, $gam = \frac{h}{10}$, $N_{init} = 1000$, and $N_{final} = 30000$ has been used.
- 2: Define Delay (d^+) and k_L^+ .
- 3: Estimate the parameters from a sample of m observations generated from a $\Gamma(\alpha, \beta_0)$. Estimated values are $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}_0$.
- 4: Get the *ARL* from a CUSUM scheme designed with estimated parameters $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}_0$. Adjust h^+ for $\hat{\alpha}$. Assume a gamma distribution $x_i \sim \Gamma(\alpha, \beta_0)$ for *ARL* calculation.
- 5: Estimate $D_i = \max\{0, D_{(i-1)} - gam \times y_i\}$, where

$$y_i = \begin{cases} b - 1 & \text{if } \frac{1}{h} \sum_{j=1}^h r_{l_{ij}} < (1 - a) \times ARLo \\ b & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

- 6: Repeat steps 2 to 5 $N_{init} + N_{final}$ times.
- 7: Calculate Δ_h^+ using

$$\Delta_h^+ = \frac{1}{N_{final}} \sum_{i=N_{init}+1}^{N_{init}+N_{final}} D_i$$

The relationship of Δ_h^+ values was found to be linear, following a pattern of $1/\sqrt{(n)}$, similar to that proposed by Capizzi and Masarotto (2020). Therefore, for values not directly available in tables A1 to A12, linear interpolation proves to be an accurate method for calculating Δ_h^+ , using

$$\Delta_h^+ = \Delta_{h_i} + \frac{\Delta_{h_{i+1}} - \Delta_{h_i}}{\frac{1}{\sqrt{n_{i+1}}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_i}}} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{n_i}} \right). \quad (15)$$

A sensitivity analysis IC with various scenarios, using different combinations of d^+ and k_L^+ , allowed for the evaluation of the Average Run Length (*ARL*) and the Standard Deviation of the *ARL* (*SDARL*). The results, shown in Tables 5 and 6, indicate that

Table 5. Values of AARL and SDARL in control (IC) for $\alpha = 1$ and $\hat{\beta}$, $\beta_1 = 1.5$, $h^+ = 8.6855122$, $k^+ = 1.386294$, $ARL_0 = 300$, $n = 300$, $d^+ = \{25, 50, 75, 100\}$ and $k_L^+ = \{1, 2, 1.386294\}$.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$P(ARL < 330)$	AARL	SDARL
2.8922	50	1	0.0456	559.7097	105.9033
0.9744	50	2	0.0476	417.3579	49.1431
1.0757	50	1.386294	0.0508	422.8127	52.7258
2.2660	25	1	0.0564	485.6308	80.8522
0.7135	25	2	0.0504	398.8045	40.4184
0.8447	25	1.386294	0.0484	404.6939	43.6148
3.0072	75	1	0.0494	584.6280	118.7730
1.2671	75	2	0.0482	441.4163	60.1657
1.3204	75	1.386294	0.0446	444.1536	62.0896
3.1843	100	1	0.0504	613.4870	131.0529
1.4937	100	2	0.0462	462.0394	70.1722
1.5697	100	1.386294	0.0454	467.9051	73.5277

Table 6. Values of AARL and SDARL in control (IC) for $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$, $\beta_1 = 1.5$, $k^+ = 1.386294$, $ARL_0 = 300$, $n = 300$, $d^+ = \{25, 50, 75, 100\}$ and $k_L^+ = \{1, 2, 1.386294\}$.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$P(ARL < 330)$	AARL	SDARL
3.3803	50	1	0.0502	739.2895	266.8299
2.3474	50	2	0.0514	554.8490	168.7767
2.5664	50	1.386294	0.0456	574.6213	188.1976
3.0646	25	1	0.0486	664.5528	216.1500
2.2446	25	2	0.0452	554.0161	170.7006
2.5524	25	1.386294	0.0482	570.8183	183.0902
3.7106	75	1	0.0506	812.4502	316.5883
2.4040	75	2	0.0586	558.4489	176.1636
2.6635	75	1.386294	0.0472	591.4529	190.4296
3.6003	100	1	0.0558	803.8699	339.2417
2.6297	100	2	0.0454	580.5249	179.7058
2.6615	100	1.386294	0.0496	592.7825	192.1011

the best performance and controlled variability are achieved with a slight delay and a k_L^+ value greater than k^+ . This strategy is effective for determining appropriate Δ_h^+ values for our CUSUM chart aimed at gamma distributions.

The analysis highlighted the combination $d^+ = 25$ and $k_L^+ = 2$ for its lower variability and guaranteed better performance, considering scenarios with known α and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ with values of $h^+ = 8.655512$, $\beta_1 = 1.5$, $k^+ = 1.386294$, and $n = 300$, as well as the scenario where both $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ are estimated with the aforementioned values.

The OC process analysis focused on the speed of detecting anomalous points. Tables 7 to 12 show that as τ increases, the control chart more quickly identifies points out of control, again highlighting the combination of $d^+ = 25$ and $k_L^+ = 2$ for its effectiveness in detection and reduced variability in the performance of the CUSUM chart for gamma distributions. This analysis considered scenarios with known α and estimated $\hat{\beta}$, as well as estimated $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$, with value $\tau = \{1, 50, 100\}$ and $\beta = \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

4. Performance Assessment

We now jump into a detailed evaluation of the proposed learning approach after calibrating our scheme with Algorithm 2 using learning parameters $d^+ = 25$ and $k_L^+ = 2$

Box-and-whisker plots in Figures 1 and 2, where whiskers values are defined by ARL quantiles 0.05 and 0.95, helps us compare conditional ARL values between cautious learning and no learning approaches. Figure 1 assumes known values of α , a

Table 7. Out-of-Control AARL and SDRAL values in a scenario known α and $\hat{\beta}$ with $\tau = 1$ for various β values: $\{2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$\beta = 2$		$\beta = 3$		$\beta = 4$		$\beta = 5$	
			AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL
2.8922	50	1	17.0653	2.3007	8.8161	0.7857	6.4281	0.4855	5.2629	0.3445
0.9744	50	2	14.5631	1.9448	7.7458	0.6801	5.7314	0.4224	4.7546	0.3037
1.0757	50	1.386294	14.6712	1.9572	7.8171	0.6897	5.7679	0.4178	4.7883	0.3072
2.2660	25	1	16.1551	2.2083	8.4678	0.7556	6.1803	0.4593	5.1039	0.3367
0.7135	25	2	14.1674	1.7725	7.6130	0.6658	5.6408	0.4026	4.6845	0.2990
0.8447	25	1.386294	14.4143	1.8843	7.6939	0.6821	5.6882	0.4163	4.7238	0.3013
3.0072	75	1	17.1843	2.3409	8.9035	0.7996	6.4676	0.4930	5.2901	0.3460
1.2671	75	2	14.9492	1.9820	7.9172	0.6986	5.8302	0.4242	4.8419	0.3149
1.3204	75	1.386294	15.0200	2.0294	7.9559	0.7113	5.8510	0.4301	4.8530	0.3120
3.1843	100	1	17.4713	2.3777	9.0113	0.8031	6.5267	0.4822	5.3448	0.3568
1.4937	100	2	15.2649	2.0926	8.0453	0.7130	5.9005	0.4289	4.8872	0.3160
1.5697	100	1.386294	15.3464	2.0867	8.0879	0.7247	5.9540	0.4388	4.9140	0.3075

Table 8. Out-of-Control AARL and SDRAL values in a scenario known α and $\hat{\beta}$ with $\tau = 50$ for various β values: {2, 3, 4, 5}.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$\beta = 2$		$\beta = 3$		$\beta = 4$		$\beta = 5$	
			AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL
2.8922	50	1	14.7039	2.4771	7.7553	0.9936	5.6669	0.6491	4.6910	0.4938
0.9744	50	2	12.0153	1.4303	6.4651	0.7043	4.8238	0.5155	4.0424	0.4080
1.0757	50	1.386294	12.1487	1.6353	6.5480	0.8033	4.8925	0.5466	4.0921	0.4343
2.2660	25	1	13.5596	1.6732	7.1987	0.7298	5.3325	0.4956	4.4305	0.3834
0.7135	25	2	11.7851	0.9901	6.3335	0.4690	4.7363	0.3370	3.9721	0.2725
0.8447	25	1.386294	11.9276	1.0402	6.4135	0.5102	4.7951	0.3612	4.0111	0.2944
3.0072	75	1	15.2914	2.9387	7.9113	1.1376	5.7812	0.7143	4.7638	0.5312
1.2671	75	2	12.8246	2.5395	6.7920	1.0549	5.0455	0.6841	4.2006	0.5239
1.3204	75	1.386294	12.8736	2.5961	6.8323	1.0846	5.0572	0.6970	4.2163	0.5199
3.1843	100	1	15.5446	2.9696	8.0403	1.1188	5.8527	0.7104	4.8085	0.5343
1.4937	100	2	13.0607	2.6883	6.9394	1.0844	5.1452	0.7029	4.2771	0.5340
1.5697	100	1.386294	13.2177	2.7235	6.9786	1.0560	5.1651	0.7103	4.2925	0.5274

Table 9. Out-of-Control AARL and SDRAL values in a scenario known α and $\hat{\beta}$ with $\tau = 100$ for various β values: {2, 3, 4, 5}.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$\beta = 2$		$\beta = 3$		$\beta = 4$		$\beta = 5$	
			AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL
2.8922	50	1	13.1494	2.0792	6.9607	0.9517	5.1288	0.6565	4.2553	0.5282
0.9744	50	2	10.6366	1.2122	5.7444	0.6041	4.2790	0.4428	3.5872	0.3672
1.0757	50	1.386294	10.8139	1.2608	5.8252	0.6509	4.3494	0.4641	3.6185	0.3885
2.2660	25	1	12.0742	1.6306	6.4616	0.7706	4.7822	0.5411	3.9748	0.4327
0.7135	25	2	10.3130	0.9754	5.5650	0.4886	4.1600	0.3464	3.4900	0.2828
0.8447	25	1.386294	10.4711	1.0322	5.6482	0.5064	4.2141	0.3640	3.5339	0.2976
3.0072	75	1	13.4339	2.3654	7.1418	1.0624	5.2462	0.7171	4.3435	0.5817
1.2671	75	2	11.1364	1.5156	5.9863	0.7470	4.4523	0.5677	3.7177	0.4700
1.3204	75	1.386294	11.2133	1.5609	5.9834	0.8080	4.4671	0.5738	3.7349	0.4806
3.1843	100	1	14.3472	2.9544	7.5004	1.2492	5.4645	0.8503	4.5150	0.6615
1.4937	100	2	11.3976	1.9676	6.0958	1.0039	4.5694	0.7282	3.8011	0.5912
1.5697	100	1.386294	11.5444	2.1591	6.2189	1.0664	4.6251	0.7665	3.8683	0.6258

Table 10. Out-of-Control AARL and SDRAL values in a scenario known $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ with $\tau = 1$ for various β values: {2, 3, 4, 5}.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$\beta = 2$						$\beta = 3$						$\beta = 4$						$\beta = 5$					
			AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL	
3.3803	50	1	17.6764	2.8803	9.1246	1.0473	6.5946	0.6427	5.4005	0.4647																
2.3474	50	2	16.3564	2.5816	8.5724	0.9840	6.2394	0.5932	5.1158	0.4324																
2.5664	50	1.386294	16.6597	2.6713	8.6729	0.9658	6.3125	0.5977	5.1814	0.4443																
3.0646	25	1	17.2963	2.7480	8.9253	1.0157	6.5121	0.6342	5.3265	0.4677																
2.2446	25	2	16.2637	2.4964	8.4664	0.9298	6.1975	0.5962	5.1028	0.4355																
2.5524	25	1.386294	16.6028	2.5744	8.6629	1.0003	6.3037	0.5962	5.1785	0.4495																
3.7106	75	1	18.1050	2.9618	9.3312	1.0702	6.7193	0.6590	5.4987	0.4883																
2.4040	75	2	16.3715	2.6003	8.5626	0.9618	6.2570	0.5872	5.1422	0.4340																
2.6635	75	1.386294	16.7090	2.6642	8.7366	0.9943	6.3352	0.6020	5.1968	0.4356																
3.6003	100	1	17.9614	2.9293	9.2545	1.0853	6.6743	0.6542	5.4555	0.4735																
2.6297	100	2	16.7865	2.6459	8.7169	0.9892	6.3391	0.6127	5.2056	0.4480																
2.6615	100	1.386294	16.8198	2.7182	8.7054	1.0043	6.3221	0.5927	5.2014	0.4465																

Table 11. Out-of-Control AARL and SDRAL values in a scenario known $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ with $\tau = 50$ for various β values: {2, 3, 4, 5}.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$\beta = 2$		$\beta = 3$		$\beta = 4$		$\beta = 5$	
			AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL	AARL	SDRAL
3.3803	50	1	15.4631	2.8679	8.0339	1.2019	5.8382	0.7883	4.8381	0.5902
2.3474	50	2	13.8275	1.9870	7.2916	0.9506	5.3700	0.6505	4.4578	0.5041
2.5664	50	1.386294	14.1435	2.1857	7.4432	1.0064	5.4819	0.6866	4.5524	0.5370
3.0646	25	1	14.6223	2.2900	7.7142	0.9989	5.6547	0.6543	4.6881	0.5023
2.2446	25	2	13.8435	1.7715	7.2786	0.7892	5.3501	0.5417	4.4565	0.4140
2.5524	25	1.386294	14.1824	1.9085	7.4373	0.8369	5.4685	0.5645	4.5292	0.4350
3.7106	75	1	16.2563	3.4528	8.3019	1.3424	6.0468	0.8582	4.9689	0.6494
2.4040	75	2	14.4365	3.0707	7.5293	1.2930	5.5250	0.8348	4.5748	0.6192
2.6635	75	1.386294	14.8055	3.1947	7.6645	1.2995	5.6306	0.8417	4.6647	0.6272
3.6003	100	1	16.0508	3.4134	8.2753	1.3374	6.0162	0.8649	4.9282	0.6369
2.6297	100	2	14.6382	3.1648	7.6973	1.2863	5.6112	0.8157	4.6665	0.6164
2.6615	100	1.386294	14.8542	3.2463	7.6921	1.2853	5.6123	0.8218	4.6529	0.6300

Table 12. Out-of-Control AARL and SDRAL values in a scenario known $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ with $\tau = 100$ for various β values: $\{2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

Δ_h^+	d^+	k_L^+	$\beta = 2$						$\beta = 3$						$\beta = 4$						$\beta = 5$					
			AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL		AARL		SDRAL	
3.3803	50	1	14.0000	2.6297	7.3512	1.1925	5.3750	0.7986	4.4692	0.6346																
2.3474	50	2	12.5448	1.9595	6.6604	0.9412	4.9178	0.6550	4.1019	0.5232																
2.5664	50	1.386294	12.9487	2.0410	6.8201	0.9917	5.0156	0.6786	4.1786	0.5496																
3.0646	25	1	13.2997	2.3926	7.0251	1.0743	5.1731	0.7342	4.2933	0.5709																
2.2446	25	2	12.5016	1.8900	6.5954	0.8946	4.8989	0.6186	4.0566	0.4772																
2.5524	25	1.386294	12.8448	2.0091	6.7699	0.9579	4.9879	0.6445	4.1478	0.5102																
3.7106	75	1	14.6020	2.8225	7.6215	1.2439	5.5506	0.8442	4.6024	0.6538																
2.4040	75	2	12.7834	2.1692	6.7606	1.0466	4.9542	0.7325	4.1216	0.5863																
2.6635	75	1.386294	13.0887	2.2673	6.9029	1.0949	5.0741	0.7710	4.1993	0.6169																
3.6003	100	1	14.9132	3.4002	7.7257	1.4505	5.6517	0.9698	4.6674	0.7359																
2.6297	100	2	12.9087	2.4575	6.8083	1.2038	5.0489	0.8552	4.2083	0.6647																
2.6615	100	1.386294	13.1398	2.6106	6.9549	1.2648	5.1176	0.8897	4.2409	0.7032																

common situation when considering how widespread exponential models and Poisson processes are used. Figure 2 considers both α and β are estimated. It is observable, when comparing figures 4 and 1(b) that the introduction of a learning scheme reduces the uncertainty of the IC ARL significantly. Instance, variability in a no learning scenario, when $n = 100$, can go up to 10 thousand, while it stays on the thousands when learning is introduced.

Figure 1. In-Control ARL performance with known α and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ $k^+ = 1.3862$. (a) Scheme without learning, (b) Learning scheme ($d^+ = 25$, $k_L^+ = 2$). Notes: Boxplot whiskers set to the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles. The dotted horizontal line represents the desired minimum ARL of 330, based on a target value of 370. "n" denotes the sample size and used 10000 replicate.

Figure 2. In-Control ARL performance with α and β estimated. (a) Scheme without learning, (b) Learning scheme ($d^+ = 25$, $k_L^+ = 2$). Notes: Boxplot whiskers set to the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles. The dotted horizontal line represents the desired minimum ARL of 330, based on a target value of 370. "n" denotes the sample size used with 10000 replicate.

OC performance can be observed in figures 3 and 4. It should be noted that OC performance is affected by the change-point (Wu 2005) τ , i.e., the moment of the change, and the level of the the change in β . Because we are dealing with a learning procedure, and learning happens over time, this is expected. The more IC observations a chart incorporates into learning, the more accurate estimators we have, and the closer performance gets to a situation with known parameters in terms of location and spread. Figure 3 shows performance of our proposed approach when $d^+ = 25$, $k_L^+ = 2$, $\Delta_h^+ = 0.7135$, and a Phase I sample $n = 300$, when α is known and β is estimated with maximum likelihood. Change-points $\tau = 1, 50, 100$ were used to generate the

three boxplots within each subfigure. Before time τ_{β_1} , observations were IC gamma with a shape $\alpha = 1$ and scale $\beta_0 = 1$. Starting at τ_{β_1} , the sequence changed to a β_1 . Target IC $ARL_0 = 370$ was used in each case following an allowance k^+ calibrated for $\beta_1/\beta_0 = 1.5$, or $k^+(1.5)$. For instance, the first boxplot in Subfigure 4, when $\tau_{(\beta=2)} = 1$, shows conditional ARL performance when a change in the process happens at the very start of the monitoring stage. At this point the scale parameter of the gamma process changes to $\beta_1 = 2$. This boxplot indicates that the 5% quantile of conditional ARLs is a bit lower than 12, median is close to 14, and 95% quantile is above 16. When the change-point moves to 50, boxplot values and their spread get reduced, even more when the change-point get to 100. Subfigures 4 to 4 repeat this behavior in a smaller range or conditional ARL values, which indicates higher power to detect changes of $\beta_1 = 3, 4$ and 5, respectively. Readers should note how the ordinate's scale is adjusted with each subplot to account for the range of ARL values. Results for a situation where α needs to be estimated are found in Figure 4. In this second case, conditional ARL values a greater, as expected, but not for much, and the behavior for different change-points and change levels of β_1 follows previous path. 10000 replicates were used for each ARL value.

Comparing results with a no learning approach is as easy as looking at performance when $\tau = 1$. No extra chart is really needed. When there is no learning, monitored observations are directly compared with Phase I observations. Independently of the change-point τ , OC behavior of a no learning approach closely match situations where $\tau = 1$. At least this is the case with CUSUM, EWMA and Shewhart type charts, where their behavior quickly moves to a steady stated with little to no change in performance. This is not necessary the case of some questionable approaches found in literature as described by Knoth et al.(Knoth et al. 2023).

As a final note in performance, we are omitting results with different values of α to avoid redundancy. This is because relative performance when comparing with no learning scenarios, different change-points and different levels of change in β remain unchanged. Same is said when dealing with a downward CUSUM. Results are equivalent.

(a) $ARL_o = 370, \Gamma(1; 2)$

(b) $ARL_o = 370, \Gamma(1; 3)$

(c) $ARL_o = 370, \Gamma(1; 4)$

(d) $ARL_o = 370, \Gamma(1; 5)$

Figure 3. Out-of-Control Performance with Cautious Learning using $\beta_1 = 1.5$, $d^+ = 25$, $k_L^+ = 2$, $\Delta_h^+ = 0.7135$, and $n = 300$ for known α and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ at various $\tau = 1, 50, 100$. (a) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 2)$, (b) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 3)$, (c) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 4)$, and (d) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 5)$. Notes: Boxplot whiskers set to the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles, and $ARL_o = 370$ and used 10000 replicate.

Figure 4. Out-of-Control Performance with Cautious Learning using $\beta_1 = 1.5$, $d^+ = 25$, $k_L^+ = 2$, $\Delta_h^+ = 2.2446$, and $n = 300$ for $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated at various $\tau = 1, 50, 100$. (a) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 2)$, (b) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 3)$, (c) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 4)$, and (d) Scheme for $\Gamma(1; 5)$. Notes: Boxplot whiskers set to the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles, and $ARL_o = 370$ and used 10000 replicate.

5. APPLICATION

To demonstrate the practical application of the proposed CUSUM chart for gamma observations with guaranteed performance and cautious learning, we analyzed data from a multi-head weighing machine used in manufacturing. This machine was equipped with a series of weighing hoppers, which were reconfigured into subsets to determine the weight of a package's content. During the process, the hoppers weigh the products and select those whose sum is greater and closer to a specific target (T), as reported by Pulido-Rojano, García-Díaz, and Giner-Bosch (2015), Pulido Rojano (2017) and Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz, and Tercero-Gómez (2023) in his study on multi-objective optimization. The machine distributes the product weights into groups of weighing hoppers, relying on a computerized algorithm to find the best combination for quick and accurate dosing.

In line with the study, we employed an upward CUSUM control chart with estimated parameters to monitor the process. Considering that the excess weight of a product conforms to a gamma distribution, a sample of $n = 200$ observations was gathered in a Phase I study, as indicated in Table B1 in appendix (Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz, and Tercero-Gómez 2023). The values of α and β were estimated as $\hat{\alpha} = 1.067$ and $\hat{\beta}_0 = 0.2760$, respectively. Setting $k^+(2) = 1.4793$. To maintain effective process control with an ARL of 500 and ensure optimal performance, we adopted $h^+ = 6.5081$. The determination of h^+ was conducted using Newton's polynomial interpolation, as suggested by Madrid in his work on CUSUM (refer to Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz,

and Tercero-Gómez (2023)). In this approach, aimed at demonstrating guaranteed performance with cautious learning, a $\Delta_h^+ = 2.9819$ was employed, derived from table A8 in the appendix, under the assumption that $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ are estimated values and considering an $\alpha_0 = 1$, close to the estimated $\hat{\alpha}$. Upon establishing the chart, we proceeded to monitor 500 observations, as detailed in Table B2 in the appendix. To control the moment of change, we added an artificial increase by a factor of 2.5 to the last 50 observations. A graphical representation of this data is depicted in Figure 5. Evaluation with the proposed chart can be seen in 5. This figure illustrates how the adjusted upper limit H^+ converges towards h^+ as it learns from the monitored results. Monitoring stopped at the OC signal.

Figure 5. Upward CUSUM control chart to monitor 500 observations. First 450 observations are in-control. Parameters estimated from a previous Phase I of $n = 200$ observations were $\hat{\alpha} = 1.067$, $\hat{\beta}_0 = 0.2760$, $\beta_1 = 2$, and $k^+ = 1.4793$. To obtain a guaranteed performance with cautious learning we used an $ARL = 500$, $h^+ = 6.5081$, $\Delta_h^+ = 2.9818$, $k_L^+ = 2$, $d^+ = 25$. An artificial increment in scale of 2.5 was added to the last 50 observations.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, a CUSUM scheme for gamma observations with guaranteed performance was introduced, integrating a cautious learning approach to its parameter estimates, aimed at detecting both upward and downward scale changes. Although the chart is optimal when parameters are known, it has been modified to accommodate the estimation of shape and scale parameters, and providing a guaranteed minimum performance concurrently. For performance evaluation, extensive Montecarlo simulation was used to assess the behavior of the conditional ARL distribution and obtain statistics such as AARL and SDARL. Results were compared with the approach that only guarantees a minimum performance with no learning scheme. Performance was examined in both two main contexts: when shape parameter α is known, and when it is estimated from a Phase I. Results show that the CUSUM chart with guaranteed performance and cautious parameter learning significantly improves power, while IC performance is assured with a pre-established confidence level. Traditional approaches are adversely affected when parameter estimation is necessary, requiring large samples, often unfea-

sible, to achieve the desired performance with an acceptable confidence level. However, this limitation is overcome with a guaranteed performance approach, and significantly improves when a chart is designed with a cautious learning scheme. Implementation was facilitated by proposing tables and numerical approximations, demonstrating their use when the shape parameter α is known and the scale parameter β is estimated, or when both need to be estimated. Although Capizzi and Masarotto (2020) proposed incorporating concurrent learning elements in monitoring to mitigate the negative impact of estimation with an increase in power, always maintaining a guaranteed minimum performance, this proposal had only been developed for symmetric data. Our proposal, in contrast, is focused on an asymmetric distribution.

About the authors

Dr. Harold Manuel Madrid-Alvarez. is a Ph.D. student at Univeritat Politècnica de València, Valencia, Spain. He is an industrial engineer with a master's in business administrations at Simón Bolívar University in Colombia. His research focuses on the applications of control charts for monitoring processes with asymmetric distributions.

Dr. J. Carlos García-Díaz received his BS in 1991, MS in 1996 and PhD in Applied Statistics in 2003 from the Polytechnic University of Valencia, Spain. Currently, he is a Senior Quality Consultant and Professor of Statistical Quality Control at Univeritat Politècnica de València.

Dr. Víctor G. Tercero-Gómez is a professor at the Department of Industrial Engineering, in the School of Engineering and Sciences at Tecnológico de Monterrey. Certified Black Belt and Master Black Belt in Six Sigma. His research interests include SPM, nonparametric statistics and quality engineering.

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Disclosure statement

The authors report no conflict of interest.

ORCID

Harold Manuel Madrid-Alvarez	http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4756-6664
J. Carlos García-Díaz	http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5559-7110
Víctor G. Tercero-Gómez	http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5196-3451

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Appendix A. Critical values of Δ_h^+

Appendix tables A1-A12 contain the tabulation of the critical values of Δ_h^+ for the upward and downward CUSUM control chart with different α_0 , considering the scenario of known α and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ values, and when both parameters are estimated whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. For the calculation of Δ_h^+ , 3×10^4 replications were generated.

Table A1. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values with known $\alpha = 0.5$ and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ and changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	7.2731	1.8818	0.9551	0.6637	0.4727	0.2959	0.1823
		500	7.9956	2.1290	1.1315	0.8353	0.5823	0.4125	0.2209
		1000	9.8422	2.5916	1.4716	1.1121	0.7437	0.4739	0.2658
	2	370	5.9299	1.3604	0.7715	0.5093	0.3889	0.2588	0.1668
		500	6.4805	1.4203	0.7843	0.5991	0.4243	0.3127	0.1955
		1000	7.7745	1.9280	1.0996	0.7880	0.5648	0.4070	0.2273
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-5.3163	2.7732	2.1092	1.8325	1.1640	0.7796	0.2834
		500	-5.9120	3.4722	2.6328	1.8782	1.4273	0.8374	0.3018
		1000	-7.1643	4.9903	3.2579	2.7226	2.0986	1.2757	0.4620
	1/2	370	-3.4036	1.3480	0.9111	0.6936	0.5686	0.3405	0.1476
		500	-3.6293	1.6606	1.0529	0.8851	0.6432	0.4498	0.2082
		1000	-4.3947	1.7167	1.3250	1.1242	0.7081	0.4773	0.1744

Table A2. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values with known $\alpha = 1$ and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ and changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	8.6855	1.8783	0.9901	0.7135	0.5064	0.3511	0.2215
		500	9.4981	2.0098	1.1050	0.8118	0.5558	0.3808	0.2281
		1000	11.4386	2.5493	1.4146	1.0021	0.7026	0.4690	0.2496
	2	370	6.8313	1.1345	0.6371	0.4787	0.3399	0.2318	0.1531
		500	7.4036	1.3063	0.7296	0.5362	0.3665	0.2657	0.1606
		1000	8.7434	1.6882	0.9223	0.6974	0.4959	0.3226	0.1776
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-6.2913	2.6367	2.0242	1.4793	1.1533	0.8502	0.3404
		500	-6.8415	3.5619	2.5355	1.8467	1.4238	0.9187	0.3835
		1000	-8.1546	4.3076	3.1376	2.3842	1.7523	1.4237	0.5083
	1/2	370	-3.8631	1.1340	0.8594	0.6325	0.4771	0.3292	0.1441
		500	-4.1497	1.2425	0.8716	0.7247	0.5195	0.3504	0.1586
		1000	-4.8272	1.6077	1.0163	0.8700	0.6946	0.4644	0.1914

Table A3. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values with known $\alpha = 1.5$ and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ and changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	9.5015	2.1177	1.1090	0.8017	0.5460	0.3724	0.2742
		500	10.3344	2.3234	1.2611	0.8741	0.6457	0.4412	0.2444
		1000	12.3055	3.1736	1.6138	1.1729	0.8236	0.5432	0.2965
	2	370	7.5600	0.5704	0.1885	0.0887	0.0460	0.0295	0.0212
		500	8.1449	0.6131	0.1827	0.0856	0.0486	0.0317	0.0217
		1000	9.5051	0.6557	0.1699	0.1071	0.0577	0.0391	0.0282
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-6.8399	2.6594	1.9045	1.3264	1.0529	0.7880	0.3415
		500	-7.4043	3.1882	2.2043	1.7555	1.2569	0.7761	0.3134
		1000	-8.7285	4.0438	2.9394	2.4003	1.6876	1.0926	0.4787
	1/2	370	-4.0928	1.1146	0.6499	0.5612	0.4358	0.2965	0.1340
		500	-4.3851	1.2058	0.8031	0.6262	0.4884	0.3121	0.1465
		1000	-5.0660	1.4422	0.8673	0.7977	0.5777	0.4094	0.1823

Table A4. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values with known $\alpha = 2$ and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ and changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25, K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	10.0521	5.4355	2.9746	2.0466	1.2352	0.7407	0.3199
		500	10.8979	6.4628	3.3721	2.4060	1.5470	0.7869	0.3486
		1000	12.8900	8.0784	4.5991	3.1667	2.1330	1.1448	0.4315
	2	370	7.5600	2.7437	1.6223	1.0833	0.7627	0.4292	0.1959
		500	8.1449	3.2713	1.8168	1.2576	0.8079	0.4822	0.2119
		1000	9.5051	3.8982	2.1950	1.5732	1.1123	0.6329	0.2493
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-7.2145	2.4612	1.4393	1.0807	0.6654	0.4011	0.2278
		500	-7.7847	2.8465	1.7871	1.2283	0.9046	0.5068	0.2314
		1000	-9.1213	3.9077	2.3519	1.6879	1.2110	0.6987	0.3152
	1/2	370	-4.2338	0.9203	0.5774	0.4219	0.2868	0.2069	0.1159
		500	-4.5283	1.0112	0.6211	0.4840	0.3330	0.2293	0.1223
		1000	-5.2115	1.3744	0.8541	0.5902	0.4125	0.2786	0.1458

Table A5. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values with known $\alpha = 3$ and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ and changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25, K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	10.7735	4.4440	2.8140	2.2488	1.6833	1.2437	0.5862
		500	11.6343	5.1933	3.6123	2.5836	1.8778	1.3982	0.6103
		1000	13.6499	5.8454	4.3591	3.3925	2.5714	1.5938	0.7143
	2	370	7.8737	2.3602	1.6054	1.3007	1.0629	0.6194	0.3358
		500	8.4639	2.3197	1.6601	1.4440	0.9824	0.6608	0.3187
		1000	9.8320	3.0908	1.9434	1.6830	1.2304	0.8946	0.3641
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-7.7030	0.7261	0.4627	0.4128	0.3088	0.2398	0.1751
		500	-8.2819	0.7956	0.4955	0.4066	0.3499	0.2608	0.2240
		1000	-9.6320	1.0800	0.6505	0.5276	0.4360	0.3086	0.2310
	1/2	370	-4.3942	0.3122	0.1904	0.1653	0.1474	0.1075	0.1058
		500	-4.6901	0.3089	0.2285	0.1735	0.1580	0.1393	0.1029
		1000	-5.3764	0.4579	0.2971	0.2577	0.2071	0.1574	0.1178

Table A6. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values with known $\alpha = 5$ and estimated $\hat{\beta}$ and changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25, K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	11.5602	3.9289	2.7084	2.0206	1.4983	1.1185	0.4918
		500	12.4348	4.8788	2.8747	2.2614	1.7958	1.1941	0.5106
		1000	14.4718	5.1330	3.7700	2.6501	2.1001	1.4557	0.6635
	2	370	8.1142	2.0472	1.3366	1.1115	0.7934	0.5360	0.2806
		500	8.7102	2.1337	1.3870	1.1828	0.9106	0.6029	0.2993
		1000	10.0867	2.4397	1.8614	1.4212	1.0429	0.7013	0.3583
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-8.2344	0.6979	0.4312	0.3513	0.2759	0.2424	0.2063
		500	-8.8209	0.7655	0.4527	0.3817	0.3263	0.2808	0.2127
		1000	-10.1831	0.9996	0.6939	0.5096	0.4035	0.3358	0.2345
	1/2	370	-4.5183	0.2926	0.1959	0.1797	0.1468	0.1228	0.1146
		500	-4.8151	0.3099	0.2225	0.1932	0.1460	0.1324	0.1133
		1000	-5.5047	0.4040	0.2729	0.2388	0.2046	0.1596	0.1225

Table A7. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values, with $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated, and calibrated for changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ and $\alpha_0 = 0.5$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	7.2731	5.5191	3.0107	2.1044	1.3243	0.8662	0.3911
		500	7.9956	6.9218	3.6221	2.7142	1.7550	0.9201	0.3689
		1000	9.8422	11.0678	5.6877	4.0643	2.4321	1.4312	0.4570
	2	370	5.9299	4.2933	2.4388	1.7179	1.2101	0.6891	0.3306
		500	6.4805	5.4584	3.2195	2.1743	1.4817	0.8337	0.3361
		1000	7.7745	8.5566	4.9154	3.2436	2.2568	1.3680	0.4873
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-5.3163	3.5023	2.3240	1.8211	1.3004	0.8719	0.2888
		500	-9.120	3.8382	2.7061	2.0953	1.5388	1.0315	0.2724
		1000	-7.9120	5.8096	3.8670	3.0117	2.1151	1.2590	0.5079
	1/2	370	-3.4036	1.8454	1.3481	0.9680	0.7214	0.4886	0.2563
		500	-3.6293	1.9484	1.2870	1.1674	0.9299	0.6393	0.3405
		1000	-4.3947	2.6266	1.6427	1.4301	0.8726	0.5774	0.1600

Table A8. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values, with $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated, and calibrated for changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ and $\alpha_0 = 1$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	8.6855	5.1492	3.0673	2.1716	1.4041	0.8187	0.2833
		500	9.4981	7.0449	3.9343	2.4758	1.6050	0.8843	0.3657
		1000	11.4386	11.2594	6.3085	4.3532	2.7991	1.4694	0.4557
	2	370	6.8313	4.1254	2.3739	1.6972	0.9979	0.6104	0.1874
		500	7.4036	4.9152	2.9819	2.1117	1.2383	0.6754	0.2329
		1000	8.7434	8.8565	4.2433	3.2709	1.8493	1.0714	0.2996
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-6.2913	3.3283	2.4286	1.7667	1.4131	1.0486	0.4086
		500	-6.8415	4.0961	2.5771	2.2875	1.6384	1.0577	0.4037
		1000	-8.1546	4.9146	3.9462	2.8781	2.2712	1.4372	0.5182
	1/2	370	-3.8631	1.6401	1.0396	0.7758	0.5721	0.3976	0.0927
		500	-4.1497	1.7540	1.3285	0.8422	0.6488	0.4421	0.1542
		1000	-4.8272	2.4478	1.6763	1.3279	0.9487	0.6304	0.2710

Table A9. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values, with $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated, and calibrated for changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ and $\alpha_0 = 1.5$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	9.5015	5.4766	3.3490	2.4875	1.4638	0.9309	0.3811
		500	10.3344	6.8001	4.2986	2.7936	1.8837	1.0327	0.4105
		1000	12.3055	10.0762	6.7508	4.3966	2.8168	1.6149	0.4887
	2	370	7.5600	3.9227	2.5401	1.9119	1.1271	0.6747	0.2122
		500	8.1449	4.8105	3.0764	2.1259	1.2862	0.7235	0.2266
		1000	9.5051	7.1266	4.4555	3.3696	2.0886	1.0152	0.3009
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-6.8399	4.0559	2.5188	1.8534	1.4944	0.9419	0.3836
		500	-7.4043	4.8330	2.9610	2.2731	1.5779	1.0113	0.4785
		1000	-8.7285	6.8172	3.6198	2.7709	1.8647	1.4301	0.5837
	1/2	370	-4.0928	1.9280	1.1826	0.7921	0.5821	0.3463	0.1259
		500	-4.3851	2.3000	1.2871	0.9463	0.6429	0.4187	0.1614
		1000	-5.0660	2.9683	1.5078	1.2395	0.9044	0.5554	0.2920

Table A10. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values, with $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated, and calibrated for changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ and $\alpha_0 = 2$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	10.0521	5.4713	3.3195	2.4002	1.6788	1.0810	0.4229
		500	10.8979	5.5751	3.7876	2.9644	1.7843	1.3258	0.4600
		1000	12.8900	7.0598	4.8467	3.2906	2.6633	1.7067	0.6292
	2	370	7.5600	3.2454	2.2479	1.7066	1.1563	0.7336	0.2788
		500	8.1449	3.7033	2.2167	1.9672	1.3357	0.8022	0.3042
		1000	9.5051	4.5624	2.9693	2.0971	1.6157	0.8645	0.4075
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-7.2145	4.3271	2.3850	1.7738	1.2274	0.6994	0.3621
		500	-7.7847	5.1719	2.7187	2.1453	1.4272	0.8342	0.3479
		1000	-9.1213	8.2977	4.5398	3.2530	2.0450	1.1532	0.4533
	1/2	370	-4.2338	2.3143	1.3497	0.8202	0.5940	0.3536	0.1449
		500	-4.5283	2.8132	1.6037	1.0447	0.7253	0.4284	0.1593
		1000	-5.2115	4.3229	2.7054	1.7665	1.1747	0.6864	0.2904

Table A11. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values, with $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated, and calibrated for changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ and $\alpha_0 = 3$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	10.7735	5.2627	3.5648	2.6105	2.2081	1.3224	0.6100
		500	11.6343	5.9659	4.3500	3.2124	2.4957	1.7472	0.7233
		1000	13.6499	7.4422	5.2076	3.8095	2.8341	1.8467	0.9086
	2	370	7.8737	3.0287	2.4041	1.7648	1.2953	0.9418	0.4002
		500	8.4639	3.5027	2.4463	1.9391	1.4604	0.9561	0.4087
		1000	9.8323	4.0210	2.7520	2.4031	1.6705	1.0400	0.4781
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-7.7030	4.2056	2.2728	1.6379	1.1776	0.6605	0.3406
		500	-8.2819	5.1948	2.7171	1.9761	1.1668	0.7673	0.3144
		1000	-9.6320	7.7415	4.3099	2.8581	1.7546	1.0826	0.4063
	1/2	370	-4.3942	2.4667	1.3713	1.0097	0.6238	0.4055	0.1817
		500	-4.6901	2.9155	1.5677	1.2300	0.7138	0.4552	0.2005
		1000	-5.3764	4.4147	2.4407	1.6228	1.1025	0.6434	0.2434

Table A12. Δ_h^+ values for different *ARL* values, with $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ estimated, and calibrated for changes upwards in $\beta_1 = \{1.5, 2\}$ and changes downwards for $\beta_1 = \{1/1.5, 1/2\}$ and $\alpha_0 = 5$ whit learning cautious for $d^+ = 25$, $K_L^+ = 2$. The values of n represent the sample size.

CUSUM	β_1	ARL	h	n					
				100	200	300	500	1000	5000
Upwards	1.5	370	11.5602	5.0244	3.3056	2.5539	1.9012	1.1894	0.5989
		500	12.4348	5.1484	3.4929	2.7963	2.1381	1.3846	0.5859
		1000	14.4718	6.2856	4.0723	3.7805	2.4995	1.6475	0.6980
	2	370	8.1142	3.0862	2.1198	1.5965	1.1829	0.9058	0.3888
		500	8.7102	3.4611	2.1781	1.7989	1.3189	0.9604	0.4515
		1000	10.0867	3.8946	2.8637	2.1169	1.7726	1.1855	0.5591
Downwards	1/1.5	370	-8.2344	4.1684	2.0515	1.5597	0.9659	0.5490	0.1976
		500	-8.8209	4.6189	2.5589	1.8754	1.0901	0.6604	0.2570
		1000	-10.1831	7.2517	3.8939	2.6361	1.7009	0.9308	0.2705
	1/2	370	-4.5183	2.4853	1.4095	0.9883	0.6614	0.4639	0.2196
		500	-4.8151	3.0658	1.7251	1.2226	0.7787	0.4992	0.2390
		1000	-5.5047	3.9747	1.9311	1.3377	0.8125	0.4444	0.1175

Appendix B. observations of excess weights obtained a multi-head weighing machine

Table B1. $n = 200$ phase I observations of excess weights obtained a multi-head weighing machine. (Madrid-Alvarez, García-Díaz, and Tercero-Gómez 2023)

0.0504	0.0155	0.0515	0.2852	0.3017	0.7347	0.2255	0.1597	0.6323	0.1078
0.1746	0.1581	0.2920	0.3283	0.1514	0.0316	0.2895	0.8350	0.8831	0.7757
0.0081	0.6196	0.6923	0.0665	0.6984	0.2457	0.1237	0.1304	0.2763	0.0952
0.0977	0.2230	0.5691	0.5445	0.0189	0.5993	0.3207	0.6661	0.4809	0.1555
0.3131	0.5704	0.1229	0.3956	0.0556	0.2174	0.7806	0.8097	0.1649	0.0666
0.4163	0.0651	0.6612	0.0084	0.8570	0.7382	0.5418	0.8340	0.3386	0.5057
0.2971	0.0015	0.8238	0.0292	0.2732	0.0041	0.1251	0.0498	0.3842	0.0100
0.2933	0.4377	0.0437	0.0157	0.0211	0.2666	0.2869	0.7786	0.2860	0.8228
0.4371	0.5971	0.3299	0.5489	0.0594	0.0324	0.2714	0.0685	0.2041	0.1279
0.2796	0.4779	0.3612	0.0555	0.0362	0.6817	0.0296	0.0254	0.0738	0.0220
0.2050	0.0879	0.0936	0.0286	0.0143	0.0078	0.4101	0.3601	0.1818	0.5236
0.2361	0.0877	0.2882	0.3659	0.7187	0.2503	0.3788	0.8051	0.1446	0.2739
0.0518	0.3242	0.3730	0.1635	0.2433	0.1463	0.6399	0.4402	0.0704	0.1561
0.3935	0.8146	0.6886	0.0440	0.1217	0.6053	0.2302	0.1070	0.5857	0.5748
0.0147	0.2458	0.4273	0.0065	0.1179	0.0698	0.4378	0.0993	0.5983	0.0964
0.4286	0.4397	0.2033	0.2649	0.0463	0.0263	0.4688	0.4155	0.1925	0.2523
0.5848	0.6021	0.1999	0.1577	0.0887	0.2227	0.0289	0.0328	0.2032	0.0647
0.5307	0.0590	0.1007	0.1314	0.1002	0.8963	0.5384	0.2607	0.5376	0.8888
0.1760	0.1881	0.0206	0.2132	0.0947	0.0561	0.0353	0.3608	0.2216	0.1396
0.3158	0.8822	0.1483	0.3706	0.1099	0.3422	0.1466	0.1876	0.0099	0.0221

Table B2. $n = 500$ phase II observations of excess weight from a multi-head weighing machine.

0.05035	0.73474	0.51502	0.61333	0.18763	0.09358	0.36006	0.06788	0.19130	0.13729
0.17464	0.03162	0.02252	0.28129	0.39090	0.28817	0.80514	0.33018	0.27856	0.17506
0.00810	0.24567	0.67449	0.60922	0.22641	0.37296	0.44022	0.01250	0.63365	0.68688
0.09773	0.59931	0.28296	0.19345	0.33762	0.68857	0.10704	0.01297	0.38876	0.05884
0.31313	0.21743	0.06039	0.02432	0.44528	0.42726	0.09932	0.02243	0.12400	0.05861
0.41631	0.73819	0.00943	0.34178	0.59030	0.20331	0.41553	0.07015	0.15421	0.03708
0.29715	0.00411	0.07099	0.23998	0.06521	0.19988	0.03282	0.05072	0.04791	0.14917
0.29328	0.26661	0.75165	0.06025	0.55474	0.10074	0.26073	0.24225	0.21368	0.26144
0.43712	0.03238	0.52344	0.01125	0.48027	0.02058	0.36085	0.54487	0.10436	0.83883
0.27962	0.68171	0.01166	0.08177	0.10101	0.14826	0.18763	0.00053	0.36166	0.72179
0.20499	0.00780	0.13398	0.10070	0.66154	0.28516	0.63230	0.51601	0.07475	0.04104
0.23615	0.25025	0.48390	0.26618	0.39433	0.32827	0.88311	0.02343	0.85868	0.04077
0.05180	0.14630	0.02069	0.06363	0.07171	0.06652	0.27634	0.30328	0.13177	0.05245
0.39345	0.60528	0.60826	0.01644	0.44499	0.54447	0.48091	0.32867	0.27214	0.20188
0.01465	0.06977	0.22443	0.48814	0.14423	0.39559	0.16489	0.10515	0.60062	0.20573
0.42862	0.02634	0.26872	0.04980	0.61120	0.00835	0.33864	0.20214	0.09847	0.06779
0.58481	0.22273	0.51335	0.09783	0.61380	0.02924	0.38425	0.83519	0.36235	0.10210
0.53070	0.89629	0.06620	0.36453	0.11663	0.01571	0.28601	0.66293	0.46942	0.22790
0.17602	0.05609	0.46296	0.15011	0.19703	0.54892	0.20412	0.06251	0.42295	0.13289
0.31579	0.34222	0.21613	0.88313	0.68626	0.05551	0.07383	0.21275	0.01628	0.29804
0.01553	0.22554	0.78928	0.06577	0.28677	0.02864	0.18185	0.57279	0.37203	0.42600
0.15814	0.28952	0.43142	0.21531	0.25904	0.36586	0.14464	0.15946	0.09278	0.29470
0.61960	0.12374	0.09658	0.15112	0.69518	0.16345	0.07040	0.30734	0.37867	0.06698
0.22297	0.32068	0.35131	0.01359	0.88096	0.04397	0.58566	0.03027	0.05991	0.02885
0.57035	0.78065	0.19741	0.27715	0.06543	0.00648	0.59834	0.61538	0.05948	0.72495
0.06511	0.54180	0.27202	0.74603	0.01839	0.26491	0.19247	0.49748	0.04362	0.25803
0.00146	0.12511	0.30029	0.07568	0.27439	0.15767	0.20317	0.18509	0.56959	0.06937
0.43768	0.28686	0.04114	0.06798	0.22717	0.13140	0.53763	0.00077	0.00208	0.20300
0.59711	0.27139	0.01464	0.24121	0.16286	0.21325	0.22164	0.89608	0.04393	0.58237
0.47787	0.02956	0.62837	0.02073	0.87306	0.37064	0.00990	0.16681	0.04553	0.01041
0.08788	0.41012	0.24432	0.34350	0.81244	0.30173	0.10782	0.22630	0.16644	0.02353
0.08768	0.37882	0.23207	0.01592	0.35009	0.15142	0.77574	0.23881	0.25118	0.12291
0.32418	0.63988	0.38730	0.20226	0.14331	0.69843	0.09523	0.13535	0.66656	0.03270
0.81461	0.23022	0.02101	0.02408	0.28341	0.01886	0.15549	0.13503	0.40674	0.54019
0.24576	0.43781	0.85007	0.18090	0.39366	0.05563	0.06661	0.60301	0.24620	0.07052
0.43974	0.46881	0.76308	0.39180	0.38358	0.85699	0.50571	0.03220	0.02911	0.08190
0.60213	0.02885	0.03916	0.53997	0.43906	0.27321	0.00997	0.12729	0.32834	0.04190
0.05903	0.53842	0.68292	0.19253	0.34978	0.02113	0.82281	0.03659	0.08110	0.00634
0.18809	0.03535	0.10313	0.07286	0.13587	0.05944	0.12794	0.14547	0.05881	0.17636
0.88222	0.14664	0.21545	0.10887	0.35817	0.03622	0.02204	0.22391	0.11710	0.37895
0.05146	0.15972	0.02893	0.68761	0.33807	0.01426	0.52356	0.28349	0.68932	0.20450
0.29198	0.83497	0.87256	0.74378	0.57955	0.71865	0.27391	0.71917	0.68777	0.38983
0.69232	0.13044	0.24242	0.04696	0.27225	0.24328	0.15613	0.33029	0.58587	0.68608
0.56909	0.66613	0.28301	0.64533	0.19344	0.12175	0.57477	0.13153	0.74687	0.23689
0.12289	0.80971	0.34681	0.53546	0.22468	0.11790	0.09641	0.02378	0.25109	0.17289
0.66115	0.83405	0.57909	0.12582	0.06863	0.04635	0.25235	0.01269	0.08392	0.27364
0.82384	0.04981	0.22272	0.20135	0.03577	0.08870	0.06467	0.25467	0.27323	0.38569
0.04369	0.77862	0.25047	0.02453	0.45383	0.10020	0.88883	0.05850	0.11908	0.20180
0.32995	0.06846	0.09624	0.22466	0.14438	0.09468	0.13962	0.00604	0.05489	0.15561
0.36116	0.02543	0.25298	0.14990	0.70204	0.10990	0.02209	0.19159	0.38000	0.45623